

The problem of speculative tokenomics in decentralized science (DeSci) and possible solutions

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Abstract: The article addresses the problem of speculative tokenomics in decentralized science (DeSci) projects. Based on an analysis of existing approaches (Gupta, 2025; Weidener & Boltz, 2025), the author identifies a key contradiction between the governance functions of a token and its role as a speculative asset. An alternative model is proposed in which the token acts as a “digital receipt” confirming real contribution, and governance is separated from staking. The model includes deflationary stabilization mechanisms (burning 50% of fees), three-component staking, and a community-managed grant fund. The results can be used in the design of sustainable DeSci platforms.

Keywords: decentralized science (DeSci), tokenomics, DAO, governance of scientific projects, cryptoeconomics, incentivisation of research activity

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Introduction

Decentralized science, or DeSci for short, is a promising direction in the organization of scientific activity, capable of solving many problems of the classical academic system. DeSci is a way of organizing science that involves automating its management and functioning through specific code – smart contracts. However, like any new direction, it inevitably faces certain problems in the sphere of its actual implementation.

As rightly noted in an analytical column by Ravikash Gupta: “DeSci today stands at a dangerous crossroads, risking collapse under the weight of its own immaturity and short-term thinking” [1]. And the danger voiced by this author is by no means illusory. The immaturity of DeSci in the sphere of economics and governance naturally manifests itself in many DeSci projects, nullifying all positive intentions and initiatives. And the key problem, the real stumbling block, is the total dominance of speculation. This problem has repeatedly become the center of heated discussions and disputes both in the DeSci community and in the scientific community at large. Ravikash Gupta also notes: “The current state of DeSci, unfortunately, is characterized more by speculation than by meaningful sustainable progress” [1]. And this state of affairs will remain exactly the same until the question of a radical rethinking of the DeSci community’s attitude toward the market and the market model of economy and governance is raised.

In this study, the author does not aim to provide a definitive answer to the question of what an ideal DeSci economic system should look like, but merely outlines possible ways to solve the tasks facing the community.

To do this, it is essential to rethink the role of the token as a regulator of relations within the DeSci model. In most scientific DAO communities, tokenomics is not just a system of rewards and scientific donations, but first and foremost a governance tool. This circumstance inevitably pushes the DeSci community down the path of alienating governance functions from the main actors of

the platform for whom, ideally, everything was created – the scientists. As a result, we get yet another centralized “decentralized” structure, where the smart contract is, by and large, a tool in the hands of crypto-capital and can at any moment be reinterpreted, and, what is most terrible, revised without the consent of the overwhelming majority of the scientific DAO community [2, section 5.1].

All these circumstances prompt a huge number of talented people to leave DeSci projects and withdraw their capital. Such a constant outflow of minds and capital inevitably affects the token price, and its price begins to plummet due to a massive dump of liquidity onto the market. In addition, the reason for such a dump is not only people leaving projects with their capital, but also capital leaving without people leaving. Both cases almost equally push the price down, dooming the token to delisting, and the project itself to hopeless stagnation.

The model of organization proposed in this article is by no means intended to be a final solution to the stated problems, but it will, in my opinion, allow science to look at many things from a different angle: to give scientists a sense of power in the DeSci community and, most importantly, to solve the problem of the profanation of science by introducing total and strict decentralization of governance and separating it from speculative capital.

Methodology

To accomplish this task, it is necessary to examine and develop in more detail issues that are organically interconnected and shed light on various aspects of the economy and governance of a hypothetical DeSci project. To this end, the author uses the method of critical analysis to study the economic processes occurring within the classical system of a DeSci project. This method of analyzing tokenomics and governance involves penetrating the essence of the processes under consideration and establishing the main reasons that push a DeSci project toward the loss of internal stability, the substitution of decentralized governance with speculative mechanisms, and, as a consequence, toward the internal self-destruction of the project.

The Essence of the Token

In most DeSci ecosystems, the token simultaneously performs several functions:

- governance;
- donation / sponsorship support;
- reward for scientific activity carried out;
- pre-financing (sponsoring research);
- profit taking through conversion into fiat;
- currency for paying for articles and additional functions within the ecosystem.

Based on all the above functions, it becomes obvious that the token in the “classical model” of a DeSci ecosystem is a proxy currency that simultaneously carries a share of the governance function within the DAO.

Selling the token on the market to lock in profits inevitably lowers the price; conversely, buying it to participate in governance raises the price. It would seem that at first glance the duality of its essence should stabilize the price, but in reality something completely different happens.

The fact is that large token holders are also interested in taking profits. Their acquisition goals may differ radically, but for large movements of capital the main factor is economic incentive. Profit taking is an inevitable process that, when volumes are huge, can become a catalyst for mass sell-offs and lower the token price even further.

As for the second essential side of the token (the governance side), it will in any case not play the role of a serious stabilizer, since a large token holder only needs to maintain the proportion of their tokens relative to the total supply in order to retain the governance functions in the volume they require.

Problems of Tokenomics

The main problem of the tokenomics of most scientific DAO projects is the very duality of the token's essence. The economic function of the token as a proxy currency implies the possibility of accumulating governance functions through the market mechanism. As a result, market mechanics inevitably arise within the DAO project itself, where crypto-capital takes the lead role in governance, and scientists take only the second.

My concerns about the speculative nature of DeSci, unfortunately, find direct confirmation in market data. According to an analysis by Nansen [3], many DeSci project tokens “saw huge growth in late 2024 before falling at least 74% in 2025.” This volatility is not driven by the cyclical fluctuations inherent in the cryptocurrency world in general. This volatility is an inevitable structural failure of the model as a consequence, on the one hand, of a loss of interest in the DeSci project and its tokenomics, and on the other hand, of a loss of faith in its future rehabilitation.

Carlos Vendrell, a DeSci infrastructure expert, emphasizes in his 2026 work: “Governance \neq peer review. Token voting rewards incentives. Not scientific rigor” [4].

Thus, several questions arise before the community. The first is: what should the nature of the token be so that it serves science, rather than replacing it with market mechanisms? The second question, smoothly flowing from the first, is that of maintaining the value of the token both within the ecosystem itself and outside it.

Solution:

1. Essence of the Token

In the proposed model, the token inside the DAO ecosystem is in its essence nothing more than a digital receipt certifying that a community member has made a real contribution to the ecosystem:

- wrote an article;
- conducted a review;
- developed code;
- performed publishing services.

Scholium. In this model, there is no emission “from thin air.”

2. Maintaining the Value of the Token

Because in this model the token is rigidly tied to a specific piece of work that has been embodied in a specific result, it cannot be devalued within the DAO community itself and is extremely difficult to devalue outside the DAO community. However, in addition to this, there are additional factors that stabilize and even increase the value of the token both inside the ecosystem and beyond.

2.1 Ways to Obtain Tokens

- Reviewing: a fixed reward in project tokens for each review.
- Tips: participants can send tokens to authors of articles they like.

- Publication: the author can receive a share of the publication fee or tips.
- Development: rewards for accepted pull requests.
- Staking.
- Purchase on an exchange is permissible, but the circulating supply on external markets is recommended to be limited to no more than 25% of the total supply (if a decentralized restriction of circulation is possible).

2.2 Payment. Service Pricing: Fixed Tariff and Protection Against Speculative Overheating

All platform services (article publication, reviewing, merchandise purchases, event tickets) have a base price in tokens N_{base} , set by the community. However, when the market price of the token rises extremely, a fixed price in tokens makes services unaffordable for new participants, provokes fund withdrawals, and leads to a cyclical crisis.

To prevent this, a threshold token price $P_{threshold}$ (in US dollars, set by the community at platform launch) and an asymmetric correction mechanism are introduced.

Notation

- N_{base} – base number of tokens per service (tokens)
- $P_{threshold}$ – threshold token price (US dollars)
- $P_{current}$ – current market price of the token (from a price oracle)
- $S_{max} = N_{base} \times P_{threshold}$ – maximum dollar cost of the service

Payment Formula

The number of tokens N that the user must pay for the service is determined as follows:

$$N = \frac{N_{base} \times P_{threshold}}{\max(P_{threshold}, P_{current})}$$

Operating Modes

1. Normal mode ($P_{current} \leq P_{threshold}$):

The service costs exactly N_{base} tokens. The dollar cost can be anything (below or equal to S_{max} , but the mechanism does not intervene).

2. Overheating protection mode ($P_{current} > P_{threshold}$)

The number of tokens per service decreases inversely proportional to the price increase:

$$N = \frac{S_{max}}{P_{current}}$$

The dollar cost of the service is fixed at S_{max} and does not rise further

3. Recovery:

When the token price falls back below the threshold, the number of tokens returns to N_{base} . Correction works only toward reducing N – when the price falls below the threshold, N is not increased.

Example

Let $N_{base} = 10$ tokens, $P_{threshold} = 10$ dollars.

Then $S_{max} = 10 \times 10 = 100$ dollars.

- At $P_{current} = \$5$ (normal mode) $\rightarrow N = 10$ tokens (cost \$50).
- At $P_{current} = \$20$ (protection mode) $\rightarrow N = \frac{100}{20} = 5$ tokens (cost \$100).
- With further price increase, e.g., 50 \$ $\rightarrow N = \frac{100}{50} = 2$ tokens (still \$100 cost).

Technical Feasibility

ERC-20 standard tokens support divisibility down to 10^{-18} (wei), so fractional amounts (0,5; 0,001, etc.) are accepted for payment without rounding. The smart contract operates with precise values; the user interface may display rounded amounts for convenience.

Destination of Tokens Spent on Services

All tokens spent on services are distributed as follows:

- **50% is burned** – permanently removed from circulation (deflationary pressure).
- **25% goes to the liquidity fund** (forms LP positions on DEX).
- The remaining **25% constitutes the staking fund (staker reward pool)**. All staker rewards are paid exclusively from this fund.

3. Staking: Three-Component Model with a Grant Fund

3.1. General Principles of Staking

- Staking is indefinite, with no fixed lock-up periods. A participant can withdraw tokens at any time but forfeits the right to future unaccrued rewards. Already accrued rewards are paid out upon exit.
- To reduce the risk of panic exits, a cooldown period of 7 days is introduced. During this period, tokens remain staked but do not participate in accrual of new rewards.
- The staking fund is formed independently of the liquidity fund. An increase in staking signals participants' confidence in the long-term value of the platform, not speculative expectations.

3.2. Sources of Rewards

All staker rewards (both the base part and the active components) are paid from the single staking fund, which is replenished by 25% of all tokens spent on services.

The liquidity fund **does not participate** in paying staker rewards. Its function is solely to maintain liquidity and stabilize the token price.

The base part (holding) and active components are distributed within the staking fund according to the three-component scheme described in section 3.3.

3.3. Three-Component Distribution of the Reward Pool

All staker rewards (100% of the staking fund) are divided into three parts:

- **Base part (holding) – 30%**
Distributed proportionally to the participant's share in total staking.
- **Active part (spending) – 10%**

Distributed among participants who have made expenditures on the platform (courses, merchandise, tickets) over a rolling period. The share is proportional to the volume of spending.

- **Grant part – 55%**

This part is intended to incentivize stakers who send tips or donate to the grant fund. It is distributed as follows:

5% of the total reward pool – distributed among stakers in proportion to the amount of tips they sent (net volume: sent minus received, to prevent gaming). The more you encourage others with tips, the larger your share of this 5%. The tips themselves go directly to recipients (authors, reviewers, developers) and are not part of the distribution.

50% of the total reward pool – distributed among stakers who donate to the grant fund, in proportion to the net volume of donations (sent minus received). The more you donate to large scientific projects, the larger your share of these 50%. Donated tokens go to the grant fund and are then distributed through community voting.

Result:

- Stakers are incentivized not only to hold tokens but also to actively participate in community life – tipping others and donating to science.
- Donating and tipping become profitable: they increase your share in the 5% and 50% pools respectively.
- Tips remain a fast micro-support channel for theoretical scientists that does not require grant applications.

Scholium. The specified percentages can be adjusted through governance.

3.4. Grant System (Decentralized Funding of Research)

- **Application submission:** any participant or group can submit a research project, specifying a description, timeline, and requested amount in tokens. Applications undergo preliminary moderation (e.g., by a group of scientists from the governance system) to filter out spam.
- **Voting:** grant distribution is carried out by quadratic voting. Voting is held regularly (e.g., once a month).
- **Disbursement of funds:** approved projects receive tokens from the fund. Funds may be disbursed in tranches with progress reports. Unused balances are returned to the fund.

This mechanism transforms the ecosystem into a DAO-funded science support fund, making resource allocation transparent and accountable to the community.

3.5. Service Bonuses for Long-Term Staking

To increase loyalty, bonuses unrelated to yield are introduced:

- 1 year of continuous staking → right to 1 free publication.
- 2 years → free publication + personal letter of thanks.
- 3 years or more → name mention in the annual report, loyalty NFT badge, priority support.

These bonuses do not give additional weight in governance but create exit costs.

4. Liquidity Fund and Price Stabilization

Fund Formation: 25% of all tokens spent on services are directed to the liquidity fund.

LP Placement: The fund places LP positions (e.g., token/USDC) on a decentralized exchange and earns fees from each swap in that pool.

Market Making: The fund acts as an asymmetric market maker – it buys tokens when the price falls and sells when the price rises. This smooths volatility, and the fund earns from the difference between the buy and sell prices.

Use of Income: All income from LP (swap fees + earnings from market making) remains within the fund. It is allocated as follows:

- a portion is used to buy back tokens from the market and subsequently burn them;
- a portion is used to purchase merchandise for the community;
- remaining funds may be kept in the fund's reserve.

Stakers do not receive LP fees – all LP profits go toward deflation (through burning) and brand development (through merchandise).

5. Emission and Distribution

Emission occurs exclusively as a reward for verifiable actions that bring benefit to the ecosystem: reviewing articles, publishing research, developing code, creating educational courses, moderation, and other types of useful activity. Every issued token has an “anchor” in the form of a real contribution by a participant.

- Emission does not have a preset hard cap (e.g., 10 million per year). Its volume is determined solely by the quantity and quality of actions performed, which excludes “thin-air” emission and makes supply growth directly dependent on real community activity.
- The volume and attractiveness of staking are determined by the size of the staking fund. The staking fund is replenished exclusively from 25% of all tokens spent on platform services (merchandise, courses, tickets). Tokens emitted for verifiable actions do not directly enter the staking fund, but can be spent by participants on services, which ultimately increases the staking fund through the spending mechanism.
- Staking and liquidity are not rigidly linked. The staking fund is replenished by on-platform activity; the liquidity fund is replenished by on-platform activity as well as LP fees and trading on the spread. This separation of duties makes the system more robust and simpler to implement.
- Thus, staking does not regulate emission; rather, the more activity on the platform (payment for services, tips, merchandise purchases), the more funds enter the staking fund, the higher the staking yield, and the more participants seek to stake tokens. This creates a positive feedback loop: increased utilitarian use of the token leads to increased staking, which increases long-term token retention and reduces volatility.
- Predictability for participants is ensured not by a fixed emission cap, but by transparent rules: the reward size for each action, dynamic adjustment algorithms, and service fee shares are fixed in smart contracts and can be changed only through community voting.

6. Contribution-Based Governance (Separate from Staking)

An alternative to the market model of token-weighted voting can be a system where influence is determined exclusively by real contribution to the community. As rightly noted in Bitcoin Insider

[5], the DeSci community has an urgent need to shift “from capital to knowledge,” where influence “is earned through active participation, not simply bought.” It is precisely this principle that underpins the model I propose.

In this model, elections and parameter changes are completely separated from the number of tokens and are built on four equal groups:

- **Scientists** – authors of publications verified through ORCID or the platform.
- **Developers** – participants who have contributed code or significant technical improvements.
- **Sponsors** – individuals or organizations that have provided financial support through official channels.
- **Reviewers** – participants who have performed article reviews.

Each group has equal weight (25%) in determining the outcome of a vote. Within a group, votes are weighted by the maximum achieved contribution level (points from 2 to 5). Scientists and developers have a veto right: if in either of these groups the weighted “against” votes exceed the “for” votes, the decision is blocked even if overall support exceeds 50%.

A participant may belong to several groups; their vote is counted in each group independently with the corresponding score.

7. Ecosystem Expansion and Social-Gaming Layer

7.1. Scientific Merchandise, Courses, Events

- Sales of branded merchandise (mugs, T-shirts, notebooks), educational courses, tickets to congresses and conferences are introduced – all for tokens.
- Pricing for merchandise, courses, and tickets follows the same mechanism as for publication services (see section 2.2, subsection “Payment. Service Pricing”). Proceeds from sales go through the same formula: 50% burning, 25% liquidity fund, 25% staking fund.
- Course authors receive a direct payout (30–40%) before distribution, as well as reputation points.

7.2. Social Network (in prospect)

- Adding a social network with microtransactions (tips, subscriptions) only in tokens.
- Integration with ranks, badges, reputation.

7.3. Ranks and Collectible Badges

- Ranks (Master, Mentor, Ambassador, Builder, Legend) are introduced based on cumulative contribution. Ranks are displayed in the profile, give service bonuses (exclusive merchandise, access to closed chats), but do not affect governance.
- Collectible non-transferable (soulbound) badges for achievements within the project.

8. Interaction of Tokenomics and Governance

- Voting rights in platform governance do not depend on the number of tokens. Governance is determined by proven contribution.
- Tokens serve as a means of access to services and a tool for accumulation through staking. Staking provides economic bonuses but does not grant a vote in platform governance.

- Selling tokens on an exchange is possible, but deprives the participant of future staking bonuses. This reduces the attractiveness of a purely speculative approach.

Conclusion

The analysis carried out in this article has revealed a fundamental contradiction underlying most modern DeSci projects: combining governance and speculative functions in a single token inevitably leads to the seizure of control by crypto-capital, a fall in the token price on the market, and an outflow of researchers from the project. Drawing on a critical assessment of existing approaches [1,2,3], the author states that without a revision of the nature of the token and governance mechanisms, decentralized science risks remaining a “speculative bubble” instead of becoming a real tool for transforming the academic system and solving its key problems.

In response to the identified problems, the article proposes an alternative model built on the following principles:

1. **Token as a “digital receipt”** confirming real contribution (reviewing, development, participation in publishing services), not a proxy currency with voting rights.
2. **Complete separation of governance from staking and market capital.** Influence is determined by four equal groups (scientists, developers, sponsors, reviewers) on the basis of proven contribution, not the number of tokens.
3. **All staker rewards are paid from the staking fund**, which is replenished by 25% of service fees – this rigidly ties passive income to the real economic activity of the platform.
4. **Deflationary mechanisms:** burning 50% of fees, adaptive service pricing, asymmetric market making through the liquidity fund.
5. **A grant fund managed by the entire community**, replenished in part by donations from stakers. Stakers have an incentive to donate because the larger their net donations, the larger their share of the 50% of the total staker reward pool. This creates a positive feedback loop: donations do not reduce the staker’s income but increase it, while simultaneously channeling funds to science funding. Grant distribution is carried out by the community through transparent voting.

The proposed model does not claim to be the final solution to all DeSci problems, but it offers a conceptual shift: from speculative tokenomics to tokenomics based on real contribution. It allows the token to maintain its market stability without sacrificing governance decentralization or scientific integrity.

Limitations of the study. First, the proposed mechanisms have not been tested in a real environment; their robustness requires further modeling and experimental verification. Second, questions remain open regarding the verification of contribution quality (how to distinguish a substantive review from a formal one) and the legal status of the token as a “digital receipt” in various jurisdictions. Third, the complexity of the model may create a high entry barrier for non-crypto researchers from the academic system who wish to actively participate in project governance and its further improvement.

Directions for future research. The author sees the development of this work in the following directions:

- development of a formal mathematical model of the liquidity fund as a tool for smoothing market price changes of the token;

- simulation modeling of the system's operation under various scenarios (increase / decrease in project activity, liquidity dump onto the market, etc.);
- comparative analysis of the proposed model with existing DeSci platforms (ResearchHub, Molecule, DeSci Labs);
- pilot implementation of a simplified version of the model in an existing DAO community.

Despite these limitations, the proposed model offers a practical path to overcoming the crisis of speculative tokenomics. It returns to science the leading role in the governance of scientific DAOs, leveling market relations within the system itself while simultaneously preserving market mechanisms to maintain token liquidity on the external market. Only such a shift – **from capital to contribution** – can transform decentralized science from yet another cryptocurrency trend into a full-fledged system capable of solving the key problems of both decentralized and traditional academic science.

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